

EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON ECOLOGY

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Annotation: Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have great potential to solve the environmental problems of our time: for example, with the help of AI, it is possible to determine which tree species should be planted in order to adapt the forest area to climate change. Cargo transportation is more efficient, accordingly, with the help of artificial intelligence-based processes, which can be more carefully controlled for the climate. Also AI energy transition control: technical sources of errors in solar and wind farms can be identified and corrected earlier.

Key words: ecology, artificial intelligence, technology, electricity, technology.

The field of application of artificial intelligence for the protection of the environment and climate is hilmahil. In addition, their use is always associated with large consumption of electricity and resources, for example, data processing centers. Therefore, it is important to carry out environmental risks, observe direct and indirect negative effects and reduce them as much as possible. Then AI can become a driving force in reality for environmental and climate protection. To date, countries that strive for green energy and reduce negative consequences for the environment are developing and implementing programs for the application of AI in Ecology. An example is the five-point program "artificial intelligence for the environment and climate", one of the programs operating in Germany. It is important to approach the goal of sustainable design of a five – point program-AI-as well as to take advantage of its capabilities for climate and environment. Within the framework of the strategy of the German federal government in the field of AI, over the next few years, 150

million will be allocated to the five measures of the SI for the protection of the environment and climate. the euro was invested. In Microsoft's paper, Columbia University (the Columbia University; USA) published "Maria" (the Hurricane Maria; 2017.) is investigating the effects of the storm and, in particular, researching the peculiarities of its impact on the dispersal processes of certain tree species in an ecosystem. Having received the necessary information, specialists will be able to develop an effective plan for preserving species under threat of extinction, while the National Accelerator Laboratory at Stanford University (the Stanford University's National Accelerator Laboratory) will detect potential disruptions and strengthen and/or restore energy networks in time. The existing system analyzes the results of satellite photography and monitors the state of renewable sources and energy collectors. It uses the cameras and remote sensors of the Pittsburgh City Municipal Transportation System (USA) to monitor traffic flow and control the operating modes of traffic lights [1]. According to a report by the CB Insights platform, 86% of medical service providers are currently out of SI capabilities is in use, and by 2020, health sector organizations will invest nearly US \$ 54 million in such projects [2].

These will not only be the services of" viral nurses "(virtual nurses) or digital consultants (digital consultants), but also more complex initiatives related to the development of new drugs necessary to combat epidemics and"diseases of the century". The results of the current study show that more than 2/3 of the plastic waste in the ocean is transported by only 20 rivers, most of which are located in Asia. In the framework of the World Bank-funded project Closing the Loop, SI uses data from multispectral images from drone flights from Cambodia, the Philippines and Myanmar to apply a two-step approach to determining the amount of waste and its composition, the first is relevant for the effective disposal of waste, separate components of waste (cups, packaging for food products, transport containers), while further details help local authorities identify sources of plastic waste and take

countermeasures [1]. Closing the Loop is the name of a related United Nations initiative aimed at addressing the pollution problem of rivers, coasts and seas to ASEAN states in Southeast Asia using technological innovation. Under the current AI Lighthouse program, the ReCircE project, funded by the federal Ministry of the Environment, aims to improve the processing of plastics with the use of the SI and the digital passport of the product. Machine learning algorithms should help sort the waste as accurately as possible. A consortium of companies and research institutes, including (headed by Professor, Doctor of technical sciences Martin Ruskowski), the goal of the DFKI research area "innovative production systems" is to improve the secondary use of products with a large variety of materials [3]. Artificial intelligence-based developments 8 data collection within this project is carried out from "smart meters", which are being installed throughout Switzerland to replace outdated standard models [4]. According to the Swiss federal institution for energy (Bundesamt für Energie), by 2027 approximately 80% of households in Switzerland will be equipped with such "smart" devices. These meters monitor the consumption of electricity every 15 minutes, and in this way, energy companies will be able to find out what hours the most consumed moment corresponds to. Ben bowler's Swiss project is focused on analyzing data on energy consumption and consumption demand patterns based on a specific algorithm of Si. As part of this project, data collection is carried out from "smart meters", which are being installed throughout Switzerland, to replace outdated standard models. According to the Swiss federal institution for energy (Bundesamt für Energie), by 2027 approximately 80% of households in Switzerland will be equipped with such "smart" devices. These meters monitor the consumption of electricity every 15 minutes, and in this way, energy companies will be able to find out what hours the most consumed moment corresponds to [5].

"We will analyze the available data on energy consumption and try to guess what tomorrow people will do in this aspect. This information can be used to predict whether or not problems arise, " says B. Bowler. A deeper and more systematic understanding of consumer behavior is one of the elements of this equation. Another is the development of techniques designed to ensure the supply of adequate amounts of energy during precisely the periods of peak consumption. Thus, SI algorithms help to avoid the difficult situation associated with energy saving and serve to save it. A similar project is supported by the German federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and nuclear safety as part of the second phase of the "beacons in the SI field in the interests of the environment, nature, resource conservation and climate protection" program [6]. We are talking about the possibility of reducing greenhouse gas emissions using SI technologies, emphasizing their innovation in the field of SI for climate protection in terms of climate protection, the housing fund is a "sleeping giant". The use of SI makes it possible to reduce energy consumption in buildings. Rational control and control systems ensure the use of heat and electricity only when they are in real need.

Renewable energy sources and energy-saving technologies of storage and accumulation can be involved in solving this task. This will improve the energy balance and housing comfort, in addition, it will save funds. The Global Forest Watch online platform uses satellite data to track illegal deforestation. The digital geosath platform and virtual modeling technologies allow us to track and control the ecological systems of our planet at a scale and speed that was not previously possible for us. New data processing capabilities allow authorities and even the public to monitor land resources in real time [6]. The information provided by satellites and uncrewed submarines will certainly help to identify illegal treatment with natural resources. However, SI can analyze these data and make them useful. Based on the concept of " saving the world from disasters", Huawei and Enbo have proposed a joint

solution for the intellectual prevention of forest fires, hoping to make small contributions to the conservation work through this. Unlike other prevention and control systems the main idea in preventing forest fires using SI is their real-time implementation of pre-forecasting them. The investigation of the presence of lower fires is carried out mainly by detecting smoke. The faster the smoke is detected, the easier it will be to extinguish the fire, and in some cases — even to prevent its origin prematurely [7].

In connection with this distinctive feature, companies have proposed their own solutions. Smoke detection: this is done at different levels with cameras marked with software, cloud services at the base of the Kunpeng processor and Atlas products for conducting intellectual calculations. To determine the exact location of the smoke and prevent fire prematurely, the cameras analyze the captured video materials, the primary analysis is carried out by Atlas products, and the secondary analysis — by cloud services. In Moscow, within the framework of " Mosekomonitoring", an extended system of environmental monitoring based on SI was introduced. There are more than fifty stationary air quality control posts in the city. , Mainly calculating how it is influenced by urban traffic [8]. After all, it is on the gases released from the car that 93% of the pollution occurs. And, of course, they collect data from industrial facilities, thermal power plants, cleaning facilities. In order for the indicators to be as accurate as possible, new automatic stations are introduced, equipment is updated. Three modern portable environmental laboratories operate in tunuk. Natural resources are decreasing from year to year. Urgent measures must be taken to change the situation. Today, humanity has been well prepared for this for a long time: cheap, common sensor networks, IoT, improving computing power, algorithms with open primary code. All this makes it possible to more effectively observe the flora and fauna, the ocean and forests, in a word, over the environment. SI Systems that can

feel, think and learn can modernize attempts to conserve resources, help people fight climate change and use energy more efficiently [8].

According to Celine Gerverey, head of consulting services practice for innovation and sustainable development issues, SI is becoming mainstream—previously algorithms and supercomputers were only available in research universities and government laboratories, and now any startup is becoming SI mainstream, according to Celine Gerverey, head of consulting services practice for innovation and sustainable development issues - previously, algorithms and supercomputers were available only in research universities and government laboratories, and now any startup can use them. New opportunities are opening up before us to manage environmentally important systems [6].

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